

Personal finance among selected 4Ps members within Batangas City: Basis for strengthening financial literacy

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Abstract

The study explored the profile of the respondents, personal finances, and the financial literacy as well as the significant effect of financial literacy on personal finances and the significant difference in personal finances when grouped according to the profile and to propose a financial literacy training program. This descriptive-quantitative study examined whether financial literacy, as measured by financial behavior, knowledge, and attitude, substantially impacted personal behaviors such as income, spending, saving, investing, and protection of selected Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps) members in Batangas City. The data obtained were analyzed and interpreted using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), which included statistical methods such as frequency counts and percentages, weighted and composite means, regression analysis, and analysis of variance (ANOVA). The result showed that financial literacy considerably impacted personal financial actions such as income, spending, and investment. However, there was no significant influence when 4Ps members were asked about their financial attitudes toward saving and protection. This study revealed no significant difference in the personal financial activities of 4Ps members when they were grouped according to educational attainment and the number of family members in the household. However, there exists a significant difference when financial activities were grouped based on civil status. This study recommended the proposed strategies to be endorsed to the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) for possible implementation. By organizing the suggested webinars and assisting the researchers in disseminating the resources they proposed, the DSWD may help the respondents improve their financial literacy. To evaluate the shift in the respondents' degree of financial literacy and personal financial actions, a relevant study may be carried out. The study might be theoretical in nature and evaluate how the members of the 4Ps' financial literacy levels changed because of the planned action plan's inputs. The DSWD may put the suggested techniques into practice to enhance the program.

Keywords: Financial literacy; Personal finance; Financial behavior; Financial knowledge; Financial attitude.

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Introduction

Humans' primary goal is to survive, and to live longer, they must provide for their fundamental necessities, which include access to water, food, clothing, and shelter—all of which are vital to human survival. Furthermore, since money is the universal medium of exchange used to transact in return for commodities or services on various markets, people cannot live without the aforementioned essential demands. People require money in the strictest sense of the word. It enables them to buy the things they want and need. People can take charge of their lives by having the freedom to purchase whatever they want or resort to a different lifestyle.

However, money is scarce as the standard of living continues to increase, on which poor financial management can create a negative ripple effect on society, specifically on a family. As cited by Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas (2019), according to a survey, 3 out of 7 adult Filipinos answered the financial literacy-related questions correctly. The study emphasized that adult Filipinos lack the specific financial knowledge to make financial decisions. Understanding personal financial literacy is crucial since people need money to fulfill their needs and desires. People should be responsible enough with their money or income and save a portion of it for the future. Society should be knowledgeable and financially literate enough to avoid financial stress that may cause anxiety, depression, violence, and even harm.

Financial stress can affect people, regardless of their financial situations in life. Though it happens more often, it mostly affects low-income households. Not all families enjoy the same privileges or levels of success in life. Due to a number of factors, including rising unemployment rates, inflation, a lack of job creation, fast population growth, unequal distribution of income, and globalization, low-income earners are unable to meet all of their daily necessities and make a living. Other researchers recently observed that the inequitable opportunity and incorrect distribution of resources, specifically the income to everyone, is one of the main issues a country is currently facing.

It is sad to note that most of the problems and difficulties Filipinos face are rooted in poverty. On the other hand, those families who go below the poverty line threshold are qualified to seek help from the government. Furthermore, with the aim of the Millennium Development Goal to eradicate poverty worldwide, the Philippine government responds to alleviating extreme poverty and hunger. They intend to create a program by giving cash assistance to Filipino households below the poverty threshold. This financial support is an avenue to respond to people's needs, which is called the "*Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program*," or 4Ps.

Personal finance is concerned with how people spend, save, invest, and manage their financial resources. It is significant because it determines the type of lifestyle individuals can enjoy now and in the future.

Personal finance is about spending less than one earns and using what is left to achieve the goals. Podcasts, books, applications, and other resources can help people improve their financial literacy (Horton, 2022). Financial literacy is associated with a person who has the necessary knowledge, skills, and attitudes about the services or products that he or she acquires and the ability to use them effectively (Kumar & Pathak, 2022).

This study assessed the financial literacy of selected 4Ps members within Batangas City by measuring their financial literacy in terms of financial behavior, financial knowledge, and financial attitude. In addition, this study aimed to determine how 4Ps members plan and manage personal financial activities regarding income, spending, savings, investing, and protection. The researcher also sought the significant effect between financial literacy and personal finance and the significant difference between the personal finance of the respondents and their profile variables.

This paper would make a difference for individuals by influencing them to manage their finances properly while still living a good life. Researchers believed that being financially literate was necessary to grow financially and in every aspect of life. Further, they pursued this study because it empowers financially illiterate people, even those who are financially literate, to make smart financial decisions by providing knowledge and skills in managing their money effectively. Specifically, the selected 4Ps members within Batangas City would become fully equipped to reach financial goals and reduce their financial stress. This study would allow future generations to secure their future since it would help them become fully aware of financial literacy and turn them financially independent.

The study was founded on the personal financial planning theory. As King and Carey (2017) said, personal financial planning theory is the same for corporate budgeting as it is for personal budgeting. Theoretical budgeting comprises five simple processes that allow for determining the possibilities of the budget and setting financial goals for the long term. The theoretical approach also enables the development of an action plan that will assist in achieving financial objectives. Those who like to get out of debt or start saving money should consider financial planning.

This study hinged on the self-efficacy theory of motivation. Self-efficacy is an individual's generating ability, which comprises cognitive, social, and emotional skills. This idea offers a strategy and concept for raising financial literacy through an extensive understanding of the financial industry's products and services in families, which is why this theory was used because it is related to knowledge and planning (Muizzuddin et al., 2017).

These theories benefited the study because it focused on personal financial management. The researchers' primary goal was to improve low-income earners' literacy. The researchers used this framework as a foundation and guide to explain the true significance of financial planning. Essentially, it assists in the management of income, expenses, and investments, compelling households to manage their money and achieve their goals.

The conceptual framework, on the other hand, was presented using the input-process-output (IPO) model, in which the demographic profile of the respondents, measurement of personal finance, and assessment of financial literacy, especially in relation to 4Ps members, were the inputs. Educational attainment, civil status, number of family members in the households, sources of income, and total monthly household income were all considered factors. Financial literacy was evaluated in terms of financial behavior, financial knowledge, and financial attitude. At the same time, the planning and management of personal financial activities were measured in terms of income, spending, savings, investing, and protection. These were considered in the study because they would help the researchers determine the level of financial literacy of low-income households when grouped according to their profile. Furthermore, the framework depicted the process by which researchers employed survey questionnaires and limited face-to-face interviews to gather information about the study's respondents, and then the data was tabulated, interpreted, and analyzed. The study's expected output was a financial literacy training program.

Methods

The researchers adopted a descriptive-quantitative research design to examine the variables used in this study with the help of figures and different statistical instruments in analyzing and interpreting the findings. Descriptive-quantitative research collects all numerical data to describe and analyze the information that answers what, when, where, and how questions (McCombes, 2021). This research design helped the researchers in measuring the magnitude of variations of different variables in the study, such as the profile of respondents, measuring respondents' financial literacy, personal financial activities, and challenges encountered by 4Ps members in handling their finances.

The researchers focused on the population of the members of the 4Ps program within Batangas City. The said samples were based on the data gathered from the active official list of 4Ps provided by the Batangas City Social Welfare and Development Office (CSWDO) for 2021-2022. The sample size (n) coming from this population and the target number of respondents were calculated using the sample size calculator by Raosoft. A 5% margin of error and a 95% confidence level were allotted to calculate the sample size to have reliable results. There was a total population of 6,607, and by using the Raosoft formula, a total sample of 364 was obtained. Due to some constraints (e.g., lack of time, non-participation of respondents), the researchers obtained only 230 responses, meaning 63.18% were satisfied with the targeted sample size.

The researchers conducted a dry run of 10 respondents who were not part of the study samples. Specifically, the pilot study respondents were the 4Ps members outside Batangas City. The researchers administered a pilot test to the respondents to avoid reducing the sample size allotted for the actual conduct of the study.

A cluster sampling technique was used to divide a large population into smaller groups, and then random selections were made among the clusters to form a sample size of beneficiaries. According to Simkus (2023), cluster sampling is a method that reduces the cost of time in a study by increasing efficiency.

It also enabled researchers to divide the population into smaller, more manageable subsets with similar characteristics. Because cluster sampling only selects groups from the entire population, it requires fewer resources to be done.

The researchers utilized a validated survey questionnaire to collect data from the respondents. The questionnaire was built around the problem statement and related literature. The items were created using the researcher's readings, concepts from the literature, and the prior researcher's instrument. The study used Cronbach's alpha to test the internal consistency of the items in the instrument and its reliability. With the retrieved results, there was a 0.951 Cronbach's alpha; thus, all the values fall within the given Cronbach's alpha coefficients' excellent range. This means that the internal consistency of the questionnaire was consistent and reliable before it was administered.

As for administration, the researchers electronically distributed the questionnaires to the respondents via an online platform, Google Forms, email addresses, and social media accounts (Facebook and Messenger). However, the researchers conducted a limited face-to-face distribution of questionnaires and limited interviews to reach the study's total target respondents. The researchers also sought help from the 4Ps president of selected barangays as well as some barangay officials in the distribution and collection of survey questionnaires. The data was managed with the highest confidentiality, in accordance with research ethical standards and the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (Republic Act No. 10173). The findings were not linked to individual respondents and were used solely for academic purposes. In addition, the researchers tabulated, evaluated, and interpreted the acquired data results in an unbiased manner.

Results and Discussion

Profile of the Respondents

The profile of the 4Ps members in Batangas City included their educational attainment, civil status, number of family members in their household, source of income, and total monthly household income.

Table 1. Educational Attainment (n=230)

Items	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
Elementary Undergraduate	20	8.70%	5
Elementary Graduate	28	12.17%	3
Highschool Undergraduate	41	17.83%	2
Highschool Graduate	108	46.96%	1
College Undergraduate	23	10.00%	4
College Graduate	10	4.35%	6

Table 1 indicates that among the 230 respondents, most of them are high school graduates, which corresponds to 108, or 46.96 percent. There are also 41 4Ps members, or 17.83 percent, which are high school undergraduates. On the other hand, 28 or 12.17 percent are elementary graduates, and 23 or 10 percent of the respondents are college undergraduates. The rest of the respondents are elementary undergraduates garnering 20 or 8.70 percent, and college graduates with 10 or 4.35 percent.

The reason the respondents' educational attainment is mostly high school graduates is that most of them, at their time, considered themselves poor and could not afford to enter college. They intended to work as early as they could to support their family. The respondents mentioned that some of them were already married after they graduated high school, while others already had their own families even before finishing high school. On the other hand, few low-income children had parents who entered college, while 4Ps parents cannot afford the same luxury as others. As a result, they may not have anyone to guide them or even reassure them that they are on the right path.

Similarly, with Lluz's (2020) study, there are different factors that can affect students' education, leading them to drop out of school. The study highlighted that due to different factors, such as the living condition, student beneficiaries desired to drop out and help their parents provide for their needs instead, even without the availability of cash grants coming from the program.

Table 2. Civil Status (n=230)

Items	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
Single	39	16.96%	2
Married	172	74.78%	1
Divorced/Separated	3	1.30%	4
Widowed	16	6.96%	3

As gleaned from Table 2 below, most respondents are married, which obtains the highest frequency count of 172, or 74.78 percent. The single respondents get a frequency count of 39, or 16.96 percent; there is a frequency count of 16, obtaining 6.96 percent in terms of being widowed, and the divorced/separated respondents have a total of 3, only tallying 1.30 percent.

Most respondents have their own families, and married individuals are more likely to exert greater effort to support their own families, which is sometimes not enough to do their obligations. 4Ps were implemented to lend a hand to those families who were experiencing a lack of financial resources to support their own families.

Table 3. Number of Family Members in Households (n=230)

Items	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
5 and below	66	28.69%	2
6 – 8	135	58.70%	1
9 – 11	25	10.87%	3
12 and above	4	1.74%	4

It can be noted from the table that among the 230 respondents, 135 or 58.70 percent have six to eight family members in the household, while 66 or 28.69 percent have five or fewer household members. In contrast, 25 or 10.87 percent of respondents have 9 to 11 household members, and only four of them, or 1.74 percent, have 12 or more members in the household.

Most of the respondents have six to eight members of the family because the households have an extended type of family. The respondents said that there were instances where two families in one household shared both their income and expenses. The members often have the highest fertility rates and family sizes. When people get older, when they are not financially secure and can no longer depend on their government and social safety net, they often have children to assure that they will be cared for. In regions where child mortality is high, the motivation to have a larger family is much greater. These circumstances could lead to a culture that values big families.

Table 4. Sources of Income (n=230)

Items	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
Employment	112	48.70%	1
Self-employment	97	42.17%	2
Property	12	5.22%	3
Transfer	9	3.91%	4

The table consists of the different sources of income. As shown here, employment, including wages and salaries, has a frequency of 112, resulting in 48.70 percent and garnering the highest tally for the sources of income. Self-employment has 97 respondents with 42.17 percent, making it the second-highest source of income. Moreover, there were 12 respondents with 5.22 percent in terms of the property, and lastly, under transfers and benefits, there was a frequency of 9 and a percentage of 3.91.

The results revealed that most respondents have a job that makes salaries and wages for their families. This result is supported by Robalino (2018), who claimed that a job is frequently thought of as a source of revenue for employees. However, employment has a considerably more significant impact on society and individuals. For example, countries grow when more people work, each job in the economy gets more productive, and people shift from low- to high-productivity jobs. A significant percentage of the global reduction in poverty can be attributed to an increase in the poor's labor income, their primary income source. Jobs also help people accumulate human capital and maintain societal stability.

Table 5. Total Household Monthly Income (n=230)

Items	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
Less than P11,000	186	80.87%	1
P11,001 to P21,000	39	16.96%	2
P21,001 to P43,000	5	2.17%	3

It may be gleaned from the table below that out of 230 respondents, 186 or 80.87 percent of them receive a monthly income of less than P11,000; 39 or 16.96 percent obtain a monthly income in the range of P11,001 to P21,000; and 5 or 2.17 percent get a monthly income of P21,001 to P43,000.

In relation to the findings, the Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS) released research on wealth distribution in the Philippines. PIDS said that 22 percent of Filipino households are now living below the poverty line, which has a monthly household income of P10,481 for a family of five, while households earning between P10,481 and P20,962 are classified as low-income, accounting for 35% of the population (Masigan, 2022).

Personal Finance

Table 6. Personal Finance of 4Ps Members in terms of Income

Items	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. The status of my income is sufficient.	2.51	Agree	3
2. The stability flow of our family income is steady.	2.50	Disagree	4
3. I am aware of how I will manage my income.	2.96	Agree	2
4. The family's income can serve the short-term necessities of all the family members.	3.00	Agree	1
5. The family's income can serve the long-term necessities of all the family members.	2.46	Disagree	5
COMPOSITE MEAN	2.68	Agree	

Legend: Strongly Agree - 3.50-4.00; Agree - 2.50-3.49; Disagree - 1.50-2.49; Strongly Disagree - 1.00-1.49

The item with the highest weighted mean of 3.00, on which the respondents agree, is that their income can serve the short-term necessities of all the family members. On the contrary, the lowest weighted mean is 2.46, which disagrees that their family's income can serve the long-term necessities of all their family members. In summary, respondents agree that income can describe their personal finances with a composite mean of 2.68. Their income was somehow in good condition and the personal financial activities were just enough and moderately executed. Income can only serve the families' short-term necessities but not their long-term necessities because most of their incomes were not stable and steady. As supported by Morrissey et al. (2020), studies examining patterns in economic instability over time have found rising volatility among low- and middle-income families with children. These trends are especially pronounced among low-income and low-educated employees and their families and single-parent homes, with substantial ramifications for family financial health.

Table 7. Personal Finance of 4Ps Members in terms of Spending

Items	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I spend my money based on my budget.	3.13	Agree	3
2. I make sure that I keep track of how much money I spent.	3.20	Agree	1
3. My spending is often based on my needs.	3.16	Agree	2
4. The quantity of money I have to spend makes me feel quite happy.	2.56	Agree	4
5. I spend money on products that I cannot use in long term.	2.13	Disagree	5
COMPOSITE MEAN	2.84	Agree	

Legend: Strongly Agree - 3.50-4.00; Agree - 2.50-3.49; Disagree - 1.50-2.49; Strongly Disagree - 1.00-1.49

Most respondents keep track of how much money they spend, having a verbal interpretation of agree with the highest weighted mean of 3.20. On the other hand, they disagreed that they spend their money on products that they cannot use in the long term, having a weighted mean of 2.13.

This means that the spending of the respondents is in good condition, having a composite mean of 2.84. They could spend their money wisely and moderately. Sticking to budgetary spending entails knowing what one wants to do and how much money is needed to execute it at the end of each month. Having a strategy in place will help determine how to allocate the money depending on financial goals and objectives. Furthermore, only 40% of people without a financial plan believe they are financially solid, compared to 65% of those who do. As opposed to only 18% of non-planners, 54% of planners felt very certain that they would meet their financial objectives (Williams, 2022).

In accordance with the study of Bitler et al. (2021), despite the safety net programs that assist low-income families, data shows that households living at or below twice the federal poverty level spend a significant portion of their monthly income on products and services for primary shelter, health, and nourishment. Families at the bottom of the income scale spend a large portion of their money on necessities.

Table 8. Personal Finance of 4Ps Members in terms of Savings

Items	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. The status of how I save is sufficient.	2.40	Disagree	5
2. I have enough knowledge about saving.	2.96	Agree	3
3. The status of how I allot our emergency funds is enough.	2.42	Disagree	4
4. I have the self-control to buy things that are not needed.	3.01	Agree	2
5. I have the willingness to save my money for future purposes.	3.26	Strongly Agree	1
COMPOSITE MEAN	2.81	Agree	

Legend: Strongly Agree - 3.50-4.00; Agree - 2.50-3.49; Disagree - 1.50-2.49; Strongly Disagree - 1.00-1.49

The table reveals that respondents strongly agreed to save money for future purposes, with a weighted mean of 3.26, receiving the highest rank. Conversely, they disagreed that their status on how they save is sufficient, having only a mean of 2.40. Obtaining a composite mean of 2.84 with the verbal interpretation of agree showed that individuals might save a bit of their money if they are aware of the importance of having savings as a personal financial activity. In line with that, saving money is important because it will help them have a financial emergency that they have something to get instead of borrowing. It is also a way of avoiding spending money on useless things. In fact, opening a savings account with a bank is the most typical approach to saving money, thus earning interest. The cost of borrowing money is expressed in terms of interest. When a bank borrows money from people to lend to others, the person who makes the deposit receives interest.

The study highlights the importance of savings even though it may be difficult to set up and critical for low-income earner households like 4Ps. It should be imparted to the households to avoid debts that can cause stress and allot their money properly.

While saving money is important, it also provides financial independence and stability, security in case of an emergency, and the capacity to prevent debts, which further lessens the stress (Team Finfirst, 2021).

The table shows that most respondents agreed and were willing to invest their money in their future; they got the highest rank with a weighted mean of 3.13 and a verbal interpretation of agree. This obtained an overall composite mean of 2.79 with an interpretation of agree. This shows that the members are willing to invest and are aware of their personal financial activities. In an article by Dumlao-Abadilla (2021), the total stock market accounts increased by 13.7 percent in 2018 to almost 1.4 million, up from 1.23 million in 2019. This translates to around 1.27 percent of Filipinos already investing in the stock market. Although there has been an increase of less than 1% in earlier decades, this is still a tiny percentage of the population. Yet, it can increase even better if they are financially literate and give importance to investing.

Table 9. Personal Finance of 4Ps Members in terms of Investment

Items	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. The status of my income is sufficient.	2.51	Agree	3
2. The stability flow of our family income is steady.	2.50	Disagree	4
3. I am aware of how I will manage my income.	2.96	Agree	2
4. The family's income can serve the short-term necessities of all the family members.	3.00	Agree	1
5. The family's income can serve the long-term necessities of all the family members.	2.46	Disagree	5
COMPOSITE MEAN	2.79	Agree	

Legend: Strongly Agree - 3.50-4.00; Agree - 2.50-3.49; Disagree - 1.50-2.49; Strongly Disagree - 1.00-1.49

Being aware of investments as one of their personal financial activities made them capable of investing in their own even though their economic living status is not that good. However, it is important to explain more about the advantages of having an investment. Even though they already have that knowledge, it is essential to impart the benefits that they can get from this financial activity.

Table 10. Personal Finance of 4Ps Members in terms of Protection

Items	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I am aware of the importance of life insurance.	3.03	Agree	2
2. I am aware of the importance of estate planning.	2.78	Agree	4
3. I am aware of the importance of health insurance.	3.05	Agree	1
4. There is a portion of my money for protection purposes.	2.79	Agree	3
5. I have a high level of protection knowledge.	2.72	Agree	5
COMPOSITE MEAN	2.87	Agree	

Legend: Strongly Agree - 3.50-4.00; Agree - 2.50-3.49; Disagree - 1.50-2.49; Strongly Disagree - 1.00-1.49

The item that got the highest weighted mean is that they are aware of the importance of health insurance, with a mean of 3.05. As reflected, the 4Ps members agree that protection could determine their personal finances with a composite of 2.87. This suggests that they have the knowledge on how they will ensure their finances in terms of protection. This is reinforced with the study of Wherry et al. (2016), wherein public health insurance programs may improve the economic well-being of families in other ways. Public health insurance programs that subsidize medical care for family members may increase the availability of household resources for non-health spending. This was also supported by Bredenkamp et al. (2017): for subsidized households that are also participants of the Department of Social Welfare and Development's (DSWD) conditional cash transfer (CCT) program, there are Family Development Sessions (FDS) where health, education, and other issues are covered. Furthermore, CCT recipients can use their cards to obtain health services without the need for extra paperwork (e.g., PhilHealth card, PhilHealth member data record). As noted by Dumlao-Abadilla (2018), 71% of Filipinos in the middle and upper classes are aware of the insurance, but only 16% receive any insurance. As compared to 4Ps members who are low-income earners, even though they are aware of the insurance, additional knowledge can be gained specifically about estate planning and knowledge about the insurance or financial protection.

Financial Literacy

The table below demonstrates that two indicators were verbally interpreted as moderately practiced, and these indicators show adequately exercising paying utilities such as water and electricity on time and comparing pricing (Mean = 3.24). The study of Lapp (2020) revealed that in the absence of monthly billing, the increased time between billing cycles might have an increased number of days of cash on hand to ensure financial security. A utility should have enough cash to last through its billing cycle. Though it is uncommon to see customers doing in-depth research prior to making a purchase, consumers are likely to evaluate goods like electronics and appliances, streaming devices, cars, cosmetics, home décor items, and even vacation trips (Akrin, 2021).

Table 11. Financial Literacy in terms of Financial Behavior

Items	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I keep a personal budget every month.	2.73	Moderately Practiced	8
2. The expenditures are reviewed and assessed at the end of each month.	2.75	Moderately Practiced	7
3. I create a budget to help meet my financial goals.	2.90	Moderately Practiced	4
4. I pay utilities such as electricity and water bills on time.	3.24	Moderately Practiced	1.5
5. To save money, I have set aside some funds.	2.79	Moderately Practiced	6
6. I have set aside money in case of an emergency.	2.81	Moderately Practiced	5
7. Before I start buying, I usually compare pricing.	3.24	Moderately Practiced	1.5
8. I carefully consider whether or not I can afford a product or service before purchasing it.	3.19	Moderately Practiced	3
COMPOSITE MEAN	2.96	Moderately Practiced	

Legend: Highly Practiced - 3.50-4.00; Moderately Practiced - 2.50-3.49; Slightly Practiced - 1.50-2.49; Not Practiced - 1.00-1.49

According to the respondents, making a budget can at least take a lot of time. Updating it every month or pay period requires time and effort to organize through their income, expenses, and goals for a strategy, but once set up, it is easy to maintain. Finding the budget that suits them best needs trial and error. Their budget preparation and upkeep take some time and consistency, but the effort will be well worth it. This means that they have a lot of responsibilities in which they set aside making their monthly budget plan and reviewing their expenditures at the end of the month. Due to a lack of money, they cannot save money since their finances are spent on their basic needs. The lowest indicator was supported by Tuominen and Thompson (2015), where poor families do not have enough money to save up. If people use this as an excuse, they will never be able to save anything. People must be disciplined and, if necessary, "bite the bullet" by foregoing some expenses to save.

Respondents moderately practiced their behavioral finance, as shown in the composite mean of 2.96. This can be interpreted as respondents being somehow financially literate in how they behave in their finances. This means that the assessment of financial literacy in terms of financial behavior is accomplished. It has been established that financial behavior directly impacts financial literacy. This finding is supported by Susilowati and Latifah (2017), who discovered that financial literacy influenced students' behavior, including saving and lending, investing, and insurance. The higher the level of knowledge, the better the students' financial behavior is. Individuals can define, plan, and create a better financial future for themselves. A well-determined financial plan will enable one to perform specific actions and behaviors in accordance with their main priorities.

Table 12. Financial Literacy in terms of Financial Knowledge

Items	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I am aware of what makes me a credit risk or not.	2.97	Moderately Practiced	1.5
2. I am aware of how different lending institutions' loan terms influence me.	2.79	Moderately Practiced	4
3. My capacity to make selections about savings instruments based on their fixed and compounded interest rates are satisfactory to me.	2.59	Moderately Practiced	7
4. In terms of investment, I am aware of the overall risk-reward relationship.	2.76	Moderately Practiced	5
5. I have a complete knowledge about budgeting.	2.96	Moderately Practiced	3
6. I am confident in my ability to distinguish between bonds, equities, treasury bills, and mutual funds.	2.54	Moderately Practiced	8
7. I understand what it means to have a personal net worth.	2.63	Moderately Practiced	6
8. A monthly budget is something that I am confident with.	2.97	Moderately Practiced	1.5
COMPOSITE MEAN	2.78	Moderately Practiced	

Legend: Highly Practiced - 3.50-4.00; Moderately Practiced - 2.50-3.49; Slightly Practiced - 1.50-2.49; Not Practiced - 1.00-1.49

Respondents have moderately practiced in applying their awareness of credit risk and in being confident in their monthly budget, both having the highest weighted mean of 2.97.

It is also similar to the study of Pecson et al. (2019), who highlighted that indigent families understand how to make good financial decisions whenever there is a consequence, create a financial plan, be adaptable to social changes, reduce financial conflicts, set financial goals, prioritize their needs and cut out unnecessary expenses, properly manage their budgets, become marginal thinkers, have personal savings, and spend wisely.

The results in Table 12 indicate that despite having financial knowledge of budgeting, they still lack a deep understanding of financial knowledge, specifically about investing in bonds, equities, treasury bills, and mutual funds, the risks of compounding interest, and the importance of personal net worth. As cited by Yahaya et al. (2019), some of them may find themselves trying to solve their problems and frequently running out of money. As a result, people would seek external financial assistance to pay their credit obligations, such as taking out a loan or using a credit card. Individuals in the majority of industrialized and developing nations are concerned about low savings rates and high credit card debt. As a result, some countries have emphasized the need for financial education because the bulk of the new population is financially illiterate.

Table 13. Financial Literacy in terms of Financial Attitude

Items	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I am terrified about running out of money.	3.13	Moderately Practiced	2
2. I can distinguish myself as a saver rather than spender.	3.07	Moderately Practiced	3
3. It is critical to devote time to think about and preparing your finances.	3.22	Moderately Practiced	1
4. I have never been able to save enough money to cover all my expenses.	2.77	Moderately Practiced	7
5. On a regular basis, I spend less than I earn.	2.54	Moderately Practiced	8
6. To keep my own finances in check, I try to avoid borrowing as much as possible.	3.04	Moderately Practiced	4
7. I am always confident when it comes to making financial decisions.	3.03	Moderately Practiced	5
8. When it comes to my personal money, I am nervous and defensive when I talk about them.	2.89	Moderately Practiced	6
COMPOSITE MEAN	2.96	Moderately Practiced	

Legend: Highly Practiced - 3.50-4.00; Moderately Practiced - 2.50- 3.49; Slightly Practiced - 1.50- 2.49; Not Practiced - 1.00-1.49

The composite mean result of 2.78 is interpreted as moderately practiced. This assesses that the financial knowledge of the beneficiaries is accomplished, and, in some ways, they have the knowledge about what is going on with their finances. This is supported by the study of Rai et al. (2019), wherein financial knowledge has a significant impact on financial behavior and attitude. The study also finds that a person's financial literacy and decision-making abilities are significantly influenced by their level of financial knowledge. Individuals with strong financial knowledge can perform better in financial planning and demonstrate higher levels of financial literacy.

Based on the financial attitude, it can be inferred that most respondents have moderately practiced devoting their time to think about their preparation of finances. It gets the highest rank with a weighted average of 3.22. In the opposite, they spent less than they earned, which they moderately practiced having only 2.54 weighted mean.

It also obtained an overall composite mean of 2.96 with an interpretation of moderately practiced and this implies that the respondents' behavior is affected by their financial attitude in making financial decisions. The success or failure of financial aspects is largely determined by one's financial attitude.

A positive attitude influences good behavior. People can build acceptable and good money management behavior by beginning with a sound and healthy financial mindset. It will be difficult for a person to save money in the long run if they do not adopt a positive attitude toward money management (Ameliawati & Setiyani, 2018). Attitude toward money is described as an individual's conduct toward the money they own. The assumption that they can handle their finances well influences their financial attitude. The more they believe they can effectively manage their finances, the more they will see the value of financial management today and in the future. They will be more optimistic that budgeting, planning, saving, and other financial activities will have a beneficial impact on their future. Another addition is that their perspective toward the necessity of financial management is influenced by how they think about utilizing mental accounting. The more they consider using mental accounting, the more they will believe that it is critical to handle finances now and in the future. Their perspective toward the situation will be shaped by mental accounting.

Significant effect of financial literacy on the personal financial activities of the 4Ps Members

Table 14. Effect of Financial Literacy on Income

Variable	Coefficient	Sig.	Decision on Ho	Verbal Interpretation
Constant	0.812	0.000	Reject	Significant
Financial Behavior	0.255	0.001	Reject	Significant
Financial Knowledge	0.133	0.038	Reject	Significant
Financial Attitude	0.253	0.001	Reject	Significant

Note: Significant – Less than 0.05; Not Significant – More than 0.05
Dependent Variable: Income; R-square=0.384; Standard Error Estimate=0.5050

Considering how financial literacy affected income, the significant probability levels of financial behavior (0.001), knowledge (0.038), and attitude (0.001) were less than 0.05. The outcome demonstrated that income had a beneficial impact on financial literacy in terms of financial behavior, financial knowledge, and financial attitude, rejecting the null hypothesis. Some studies showed that a person with a relatively significant salary may demonstrate his financial behavior. Financial management behavior is positively correlated with financial knowledge, which indicates that a person's more financial knowledge, the better financial management behavior will be.

Financial literacy, financial attitudes, and debt management all positively impact financial well-being. On the other hand, financial literacy is considerably improving financial well-being, which has a beneficial effect (Rahman et al., 2021). The study of Lusardi et al. (2021), also concluded that there is a significant correlation between financial fragility and financial literacy. The study highlighted that many people are not well-prepared for the financial decisions dealing with a financial crisis. It shows that financial literacy plays a significant role in personal financial management, particularly in low-income earners.

Table 15. Effect of Financial Literacy on Income

Variable	Coefficient	Sig.	Decision on Ho	Verbal Interpretation
Constant	0.924	0.000	Reject	Significant
Financial Behavior	0.222	0.001	Reject	Significant
Financial Knowledge	0.143	0.010	Reject	Significant
Financial Attitude	0.290	0.000	Reject	Significant

Note: Significant – Less than 0.05; Not Significant – More than 0.05
Dependent Variable: Spending; R-square=0.467; Standard Error Estimate=0.4365

The significance probability levels of financial behavior (0.001), financial knowledge (0.010), and financial attitude (0.000) were less than the alpha level of 0.05. The result shows that spending can positively affect financial literacy in terms of financial behavior, financial knowledge, and financial attitude; thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. According to Edwards (2020), financial literacy can be acquired through understanding how to work, save, invest, and spend intelligently. People who are financially literate are less concerned about their finances and whether they will be able to pay their bills. People who are financially secure live in sharp contrast to others who are unable to pay their debts on time. Late fees, penalties, and missed payment fees quickly add up, and consumers soon become further in debt.

Despite having such personal financial goals in place, an individual or a family may still find themselves battling with how to spend their money properly. According to Schanzenbach et al. (2016), households with lower income spend more of their budgets on essentials, and as their income improves, they spend less of their budgets on necessities.

Table 16. Effect of Financial Literacy on Savings

Variable	Coefficient	Sig.	Decision on Ho	Verbal Interpretation
Constant	1.238	0.000	Reject	Significant
Financial Behavior	0.415	0.000	Reject	Significant
Financial Knowledge	0.114	0.042	Reject	Significant
Financial Attitude	0.009	0.884	Fail to Reject	Not Significant

Note: Significant – Less than 0.05; Not Significant – More than 0.05
Dependent Variable: Savings; R-square=0.390; Standard Error Estimate=0.4408

There was a sufficient data to prove that financial literacy had a significant impact on the personal finances of chosen 4Ps members in terms of savings, specifically with their financial behavior and financial knowledge with p-values of 0.000 and 0.042, respectively. However, the financial attitude of the members obtained a p-value of 0.884, which was above the alpha level of 0.05, indicating that there was insufficient evidence that there is a significant impact on the respondents' personal finances in terms of their savings.

It can be observed that financial literacy has a significant effect on the personal finance of selected 4Ps members in terms of their savings, specifically with their financial behavior and financial knowledge, therefore rejects the null hypothesis. Inversely, there is a significant effect on the savings of the respondents in terms of the financial attitude which result to failure to reject the null hypothesis.

As Duquette (2018) mentioned, one feasible technique for developing financial competence among today's young people is to educate financial literacy in school. Students will develop an economic awareness by 12 years old, which academics classify as 'essentially mature.' It encourages young people to save money, promotes family discussions, and enables youngsters to be stewards of their financial destinies by including teachings on prudent financial habits early in their cognitive development. According to Klapper and Lusardi (2020), individuals must be financially literate to make educated decisions regarding their finances, particularly when it comes to investing, borrowing, and saving.

In addition, Banthia and Dey (2021) said that individuals with a high level of financial expertise place a higher emphasis on life enjoyment. The more financial knowledge a person possesses, the better their money management behavior is regarded to be. The person's financial knowledge relates to their comprehension of a money issue that is significant to them, such as budgeting and saving plans. Team Finfirst (2021) stated that conserving money provides financial independence, stability, and protection during a financial emergency. Saving money enables people to avoid debt, which lowers their stress level. Despite knowing the importance of saving, they frequently ignore it and spend more of their money. Meanwhile, 4Ps members still show that their financial attitude does not influence how they save.

Table 17. Effect of Financial Literacy on Investment

Variable	Coefficient	Sig.	Decision on Ho	Verbal Interpretation
Constant	0.550	0.000	Reject	Significant
Financial Behavior	0.234	0.001	Reject	Significant
Financial Knowledge	0.282	0.000	Reject	Significant
Financial Attitude	0.260	0.000	Reject	Significant

Note: Significant – Less than 0.05; Not Significant – More than 0.05
Dependent Variable: Income; R-square=0.532; Standard Error Estimate=0.4679

Regarding the effect of financial literacy on investment, financial behavior, knowledge, and attitude significantly affected the personal finance of the 4Ps members with a p-value of 0.001, 0.000, and 0.000, respectively. It has clear evidence that financial literacy has a significant effect on the personal finance of select 4Ps members in terms of investment, which rejects the null hypothesis. Susilowati and Latifah (2017) said that the greater the children's understanding, the better their financial conduct will be. They are confident in their ability to make the most rewarding financial investments. Furthermore, their planned investments are expected to create significant revenue in the future, influencing their financial behavior.

According to Praba and Malarmathi (2015), individual decision-making freedom has a considerable favorable influence on promoting individual investment. Financial attitudes have an impact on investment decision-making. They can be judged by investors' capacity to manage their funds and their willingness to get financial understanding (Wangi & Baskara, 2021).

Table 18. Effect of Financial Literacy on Protection

Variable	Coefficient	Sig.	Decision on Ho	Verbal Interpretation
Constant	0.619	0.000	Reject	Significant
Financial Behavior	0.221	0.005	Reject	Significant
Financial Knowledge	0.557	0.000	Reject	Significant
Financial Attitude	0.018	0.810	Fail to Reject	Not Significant

Note: Significant – Less than 0.05; Not Significant – More than 0.05
Dependent Variable: Protection; R-square=0.541; Standard Error Estimate=0.5284

The table above shows how financial literacy affected protection. Results showed that financial behavior and knowledge had significance probabilities that were smaller than the alpha levels of 0.05, which were 0.005 and 0.000, respectively. However, the financial attitude of the chosen 4Ps members had a p-value of 0.810, which was higher than the alpha level of 0.05.

The result shows that protection can positively affect financial literacy in terms of financial behavior and financial knowledge; thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. According to Khawar and Sarwar (2021), people who are unwilling to plan and lack financial literacy may take out a mortgage. Future financial decisions are influenced by attitudes toward spending, budgeting, and buying. People who have a saving mindset can also form sound financial practices. Financial behavior indicators include future planning, budgeting, investing, and saving. However, the financial attitude of select 4Ps members does not have enough evidence to prove its significant effect on the personal finances of the respondents in terms of their protection, resulting in a failure to reject the null hypothesis.

Significant difference in personal financial activities when grouped according to profile

Table 19. Differences in Personal Finance in terms of Educational Attainment

Variable	Coefficient	Sig.	Decision on Ho	Verbal Interpretation
Income	2.675	0.023	Reject	Significant
Savings	0.648	0.664	Fail to Reject	Not Significant
Spending	1.845	0.105	Fail to Reject	Not Significant
Investment	1.483	0.196	Fail to Reject	Not Significant
Protection	0.292	0.917	Fail to Reject	Not Significant

Note: Significant – Less than 0.05; Not Significant – More than 0.05

Regarding educational attainment, it showed that the null hypothesis was rejected in terms of income due to a notable variation in the personal financial behaviors of the chosen 4Ps. With respective p-values of 0.664, 0.105, 0.196, and 0.917, the researchers failed to reject the null hypothesis for spending, saving, investing, and protection.

When grouped by educational attainment, the personal financial behaviors of select 4Ps members in terms of savings, spending, investing, and protection were not significant. Contrariwise, income was the only variable that has a significant difference as to educational attainment.

People get gritty merely to live occasionally because of the circumstances in which they find themselves. It indicates that, by mere experience, they can still be financially literate. Like what Basas (2021) revealed in his study, even most of their household heads and members had only reached elementary education. Fishing became more convenient and practical employment for them, which became a significant source of their monthly income as somewhat reasonable. Even though beneficiaries were low-income households with uncertain socioeconomic conditions, income may vary regarding their purchasing power, including health, education, and other expenses.

Table 20. Differences in Personal Finances in terms of Civil Status

Variable	Coefficient	Sig.	Decision on Ho	Verbal Interpretation
Income	3.173	0.025	Reject	Significant
Savings	2.974	0.033	Reject	Significant
Spending	4.891	0.003	Reject	Significant
Investment	4.054	0.008	Reject	Significant
Protection	3.942	0.009	Reject	Significant

Note: Significant – Less than 0.05; Not Significant – More than 0.05

Concerning civil status, the estimated p-values for income, savings, spending, investment, and protection were 0.025, 0.033, 0.003, 0.008, and 0.009, respectively. This disproved the null hypothesis and showed that there was a significant difference in personal finance when people were categorized according to their civil status.

All variables under personal finance have a significant difference when grouped according to their civil status, thus rejecting the null hypothesis. The spending of the married couple, especially when the mother who manages the personal finances, spends more on the childcare.

As cited by Sarkisian and Gertel (2008), married people have better household earnings and more education than single people. By emphasizing traditional gender roles, couples have maintained gender boundaries while suppressing their gender-atypical household earnings pattern and downplaying the wife's economic contribution. These couples focused their efforts on making their nontraditional marriages seem and feel more comfortable and typical, rather than actively working toward gender equality (Lyonette & Crompton, 2015). Contrary to married people, as cited by Leopold (2018), numerous studies have found that women mostly bear divorce's economic consequences. Women have a steeper decrease in household income and a higher probability of poverty following divorce. On the other hand, their ex-husbands may even increase their level of living throughout the post-divorce years.

In addition, savings have also made a significant difference when grouped according to civil status. A study discovered that the United States' anti-poverty program affects single moms' decisions by offering incentives to cohabit and found quantitatively significant impacts on savings and labor supply of spouses (Ortigueira & Siassi, 2022). In addition, the respondents said that if their spouse has work, they can be able to save money and can increase their income, which is also reflected in this study.

Since most respondents were married couples, investment remains a discussion towards them, considering the perception of the spouse is essential in making investments. In accordance with the study of Garcia et al. (2017), the marital status of a person has a significant influence on the knowledge of investment plans. Married respondents became more aware of investment, whereas they were concerned about their future expenses, so they must be practical in handling financial situations.

Table 21. Differences in Personal Finance in terms of Number of Family Members in the Household

Variable	Coefficient	Sig.	Decision on Ho	Verbal Interpretation
Income	1.822	0.125	Fail to Reject	Not Significant
Savings	0.347	0.846	Fail to Reject	Not Significant
Spending	2.336	0.056	Fail to Reject	Not Significant
Investment	0.295	0.881	Fail to Reject	Not Significant
Protection	1.933	0.106	Fail to Reject	Not Significant

Note: Significant – Less than 0.05; Not Significant – More than 0.05

In relation to the number of family members in the household, the variables income, savings, spending, investing, and protection produced p-values of 0.125, 0.846, 0.056, 0.881, and 0.106, respectively. The estimated p-values were greater than the alpha level of 0.05, indicating that there was no statistically significant difference in personal finances when the 4Ps were grouped based on their profile; as a result, the null hypothesis fails to reject.

According to Brounen et al. (2016), late-generation family households do not see the number of family members in their households as having significant effects when it comes to managing finances. Only younger households are considered a demographic factor when it comes to managing finances and that they are financially literate. Low-income households do not see the number of their family households as a problem when it comes to managing finances because, whether there are many family members, the income is still insufficient for their needs. Contrary to this, according to Kim et al. (2017), the most significant group that shapes a person's financial habits is their family. Family decision-makers opt for several economic activities on behalf of the entire family, including financial ones.

Table 22. Differences in Personal Finance in terms of Sources of Income

Variable	Coefficient	Sig.	Decision on Ho	Verbal Interpretation
Income	0.497	0.684	Fail to Reject	Not Significant
Savings	1.225	0.301	Fail to Reject	Not Significant
Spending	0.276	0.843	Fail to Reject	Not Significant
Investment	0.101	0.959	Fail to Reject	Not Significant
Protection	0.144	0.933	Fail to Reject	Not Significant

Note: Significant – Less than 0.05; Not Significant – More than 0.05

As to sources of income, income had 0.684 computed p-values, savings had 0.301, spending had 0.843, investment had 0.959, and protection had 0.933. It meant that they were all greater than the alpha level of 0.05, which were considered not significant. As a result, the null hypothesis fails to reject.

Individual personal finances are not significantly different across a variety of income sources. According to the respondents, sources of income do not clearly suffice the need for personal finances, given that they are not stable and not guaranteed a much higher value.

Table 23. Differences in Personal Finances in terms of Total Household Monthly Income

Variable	Coefficient	Sig.	Decision on Ho	Verbal Interpretation
Income	19.102	0.000	Reject	Significant
Savings	1.611	0.202	Fail to Reject	Not Significant
Spending	5.168	0.019	Reject	Significant
Investment	3.110	0.086	Fail to Reject	Not Significant
Protection	5.726	0.018	Reject	Significant

Note: Significant – Less than 0.05; Not Significant – More than 0.05

In terms of personal finance, when grouped according to total household monthly income, the respective p-values for saving and investing were 0.202 and 0.086. This meant that based on these profile factors, there are no significant differences in these variables, which failed to be rejected. Meanwhile, the computed p-value for income was 0.000; for spending, 0.019; and for protection, 0.018, all of which were significant at the 0.05 level of significance, hence rejected.

To support this, Filipino low-income earners are spending most of their income on food. Schanzenbach et al.'s (2016) study revealed that households with lower monthly income spend more of their budgets on necessities, and as their income grows, less of their budgets are spent on necessities. Other research studies also revealed that those households with lower income absorbed so much of their income for necessities such as food, water, and utilities away from any kind of entertainment or wants that an upper-income earner can do since they only have a limited resource. Low-income earners spent far more of their income on their needs than upper-income families did.

However, Wilson and McLeod (2023) stated that low-income earners with limited financial resources have their focal point mostly in acquiring their basic needs. Therefore, in terms of having their protection, some may not afford it since other low-income earners have a limited monthly income and only allot for their basic needs. Considering that these are those people who are high-income earners, low-income earners are way too far on investing and acquiring insurance.

As supported by Lluz (2020), subsidies must be used for their intended purpose, even if only in a little quantity. Beneficiaries must also work to support themselves. They need to invest their money carefully. They must work not merely to fulfill their current requirements but also to preserve their long-term survival. The government must figure out how to help all school-age children, include everyone in the community in promoting socioeconomic well-being, and lessen the beneficiaries' reliance on the government.

More program initiatives must be offered to household beneficiaries to engage in successful economic ventures, such as comprehensive health services, financial literacy training, student scholarship programs, and sustainable livelihood programs.

Conclusions

Most 4Ps members in Batangas City were high school graduates, with most of the respondents being married and having 6–8 family members in their household. In terms of their income, most of them were self-employed and had less than 11,000 peso monthly incomes.

Majority of the respondents agreed that their personal finances, including income, savings, spending, investing, and protection, were just enough and moderately executed. Their personal finances can be described as in good condition. Their income was sufficient to meet the immediate needs of all family members, assuring them to keep track of how much money they spend; they have enough understanding about their savings; they have the willingness to invest their money for the future when it comes to investing; and they believed that protection could affect their own money.

There was a significant positive effect of financial literacy on income, spending, and investing in personal financial activities, implying being financially stable and self-sufficient. However, there was no significant effect in terms of financial attitude toward savings and protection. Financially literate people are less likely to experience personal financial difficulties because they are better equipped to handle particular obstacles.

There was no significant difference in the personal financial activities of 4Ps members when grouped according to educational attainment and the number of family members in the household. However, there existed a significant difference when financial activities were grouped based on civil status. Even though the recipients were low-income families with uncertain socioeconomic circumstances, their purchasing power varied in terms of health, education, and other expenses. The sources of income were insufficient to meet their own financial needs. There were significant differences when financial activities are grouped based on civil status. There is a greater chance that married couples can have a source of income to contribute to their family, resulting in higher household wages and more education than single persons.

Recommendations

A proposed plan of action was formulated by the researchers to strengthen the financial literacy of select 4Ps members within Batangas City. This action plan may be executed with the help of other government agencies such as the DSWD/CSWD, together with an expert like a financial advisor who can impart his or her understanding to the target participants, particularly the 4Ps members, regarding the specified topic, where it can be done through financial literacy training programs such as seminars, webinars, workshops, and financial counseling. The researchers shall assess the effectiveness of the program with the guidance of performance indicators such as: at least 75% of the attendees in the seminar shall agree in a post-survey questionnaire about financial behavior.

Out of 50 to 100 online participants, 75% of them will answer a situational question correctly about the posted materials. During and after the event, there should be at least 10 to 15 people who will ask a question about their financial concerns to the guest speaker and share their plans and realizations at the end of the program. This is to assess the improvements for selected 4Ps members, including their high participation rate.

The selected 4Ps members from Batangas City may work on strengthening their financial literacy through the activities outlined in the action plan. 4Ps may increase their financial literacy by attending the suggested activities and honing the practical application of what they learn in their day-to-day activities.

The DSWD may aid the respondents in strengthening their financial literacy by hosting the proposed webinars and helping the researchers in the dissemination of the materials they proposed. A related study may be conducted to assess the change in the level of financial literacy and personal financial activities of the respondents. The study may be theoretical and may test the changes in the level of financial literacy of the 4Ps members.

The proposed strategies may be implemented and endorsed by the DSWD for the betterment of the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps). Implementing strategies provided by the researchers could help the department assess the said program. This study may be replicated to include other 4Ps members outside Batangas City and any other factors beyond the scope of this study.

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Appendix

Appendix A. Sample Action Plan

Objective: Strengthen the financial literacy of 4Ps members through training programs, such as seminars / webinars and financial counseling.

Statement of the Commitment Plan and Goals	Specific Objectives	Programs / Activities	Persons Responsible	Timetable (Estimated)	Resources	Suggested Venue	Projected Budget	Performance Indicators
Provide training programs such as seminars / webinars and financial counseling to 4Ps members within Batangas City.	To enhance the financial behavior of the 4Ps members specifically on how to make a financial plan for their savings and expenditures.	Personal Budgeting Training: O, Kita Mo Na, 'Pag May Alam sa Badyeting at Pinansya, Malaki ang Ganansya	DSWD— Batangas City Department	Annually	Organizer / Facilitator Participants Guest Speaker (Financial Advisor) Face-to-Face Program	Batangas City Sports Coliseum	P10,000	There should be at least 75% of the participants who attend webinars and who shall agreed in a post-survey questionnaire about financial behavior.
	To strengthen the financial literacy of 4Ps members in terms of financial knowledge.	Distribution / Posting of E-Public Materials (Dapat Alam Mo Series: Pag-iimpok, Pag-gastos at Pamumuhunan)		Monthly	Writer Editor Distributor	Facebook Pages, Distribution around the Vicinity of Batangas City Area	P5,000	Out of 50 to 100 participants, at least 75% of them will participate and answer Q&A games correctly. Note: A situational question about financial literacy will be given.
	To provide participants with the necessary attitudes and values towards money management.	Simulation Program on Money Management— Tamang Diskarte sa Merkado, 'Yan Ang Kailangan Mo!			Annually	Organizer / Facilitator Participants Guest Speaker (Financial Advisor) Face-to-Face Program	Batangas City Sports Coliseum	P15,000